

DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS BETWEEN RUSSIA AND YEMEN

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Abstract

This scientific article is devoted to the study of the directions of development of diplomatic relations between Russia and Yemen. The article analyzes the history of diplomatic relations between the two countries, the main problems and challenges facing them, as well as prospects for strengthening cooperation. The study analyzed the potential for the development of cooperation in such areas as economics, energy, culture and education. The key factors contributing to the development of relations, as well as possible obstacles to cooperation were identified. In conclusion, the article draws conclusions about the prospects for the development of diplomatic relations between Russia and Yemen, and identifies areas for further research in this area.

Keywords: directions of development, diplomatic relations, Russia, Yemen, economy, energy, culture, education, potential, problems, challenges, prospects, cooperation.

Introduction. Russia and Yemen have long-standing historical ties, but in recent years, economic and political difficulties have led to a weakening of relations between these states. Russia is the largest arms exporter to Yemen, but at the same time, the trade turnover between the two countries leaves much to be desired. In 2020, the trade turnover between Russia and Yemen amounted to only 11.7 million US dollars, while between Russia and Saudi Arabia - 1.7 billion US dollars.

The problems between Russia and Yemen are not only related to trade, but also to the military conflict in the region. Yemen has been in a state of civil war since 2015, and Russia is one of the participants in the international coalition that supports the Yemeni government. In addition, Russia and Yemen have a common problem with terrorism and extremism. In light of these problems, it is necessary to consider the possibilities of further development of interstate cooperation between Russia and Yemen, including the economic, political and military spheres, in order to strengthen relations and resolve the conflict in the region.

The main part. Today, against the background of the difficult geopolitical situation in the Middle East, the issues of diplomatic relations between Russia and Yemen are becoming increasingly important. In addition, Russia and Yemen have significant potential for developing economic cooperation, especially in the field of energy and other industries.

Diplomatic relations between Russia and Yemen have a long history that dates back to the Soviet period. In 1967, after the separation of South Yemen from the British Empire, the Soviet Union established diplomatic relations with the new state.

In 1986, after the unification of South and North Yemen into a single state, Russia continued to maintain diplomatic relations with Yemen. In 1990, after the unification of the GDR and the FRG, Russia was one of the first states to recognize the Republic of Yemen.

In recent years, relations between Russia and

Yemen have become more intense. In 2009, as part of Yemeni President Ali Abdullah Saleh's visit to Moscow, an agreement on cooperation between Russia and Yemen was signed. In 2013, Russian President Vladimir Vladimirovich Putin and Yemeni President Abd Rabbu Mansour Hadi signed an agreement on friendship, cooperation and partnership between the Russian Federation and the Republic of Yemen. However, in light of recent events such as the war in Yemen, relations between Russia and Yemen have begun to change. Russia stands for a peaceful settlement of the conflict in Yemen and supports the idea of a national dialogue between the conflicting parties. In addition, Russia also provides humanitarian assistance to Yemen. [1] At the moment, relations between Russia and Yemen are developing in several directions:

1. Military-technical cooperation. Russia is the largest supplier of weapons to Yemen, especially in terms of heavy weapons, including tanks, self-propelled artillery and other military equipment. Recently, Russia and Yemen have been actively discussing the possibility of expanding military-technical cooperation, including the supply of new types of weapons and training of military personnel.

2. Economic cooperation. Russia and Yemen are striving to develop economic ties, although the volume of trade between these countries is still small. Recently, Russia and Yemen have been actively discussing the possibilities of expanding cooperation in trade, energy and agriculture.

3. Political cooperation. Russia and Yemen maintain dialogue at the political level and actively cooperate within the framework of international organizations, including the United Nations and the League of Arab States.

4. Humanitarian cooperation. Russia provides humanitarian assistance to Yemen within the framework of international programs aimed at combating hunger

and poverty, as well as supports medical care and educational projects.

Despite the existing diplomatic relations, Russia and Yemen face a number of problems and challenges that can have a negative impact on bilateral relations. Some of these issues and challenges include:

1. The war in Yemen: The conflict in Yemen, which began in 2015, has become a major problem for relations between Russia and Yemen. Russia supports a peaceful settlement of the conflict and a national dialogue between the conflicting parties, while the Republic of Yemen is at war, which makes it difficult to develop cooperation between the two countries.

2. Economic problems: Economic difficulties in Yemen may hinder the development of bilateral relations, as Yemen is one of the poorest countries in the world. In addition, economic sanctions against Russia may also have a negative impact on trade and investment between the two countries.

3. Security: Security issues are also a challenge for relations between Russia and Yemen. Yemen is located at the intersection of the routes between Africa and Asia, and is located near the Blue and Red Seas, which makes it a strategically important place. However, problems with terrorism and piracy in this region may pose threats to the security of the two countries.

4. Humanitarian situation: Yemen is facing a serious humanitarian crisis caused by the conflict, which has affected many sectors of the economy and social sphere. Russia provides humanitarian aid to Yemen, but the scale of the problem requires more attention that is serious and cooperation between the two countries. [2]

Thus, solving these problems and challenges can be a key step in the development of diplomatic relations between Russia and Yemen. In addition, the development of economic cooperation can contribute to strengthening relations between the two countries, especially if we take into account the prospects for oil and gas trade, as well as the development of other industries such as agriculture and fisheries. [3]

In order to determine the potential for strengthening cooperation between Russia and Yemen, it is necessary to analyze opportunities for expanding cooperation in various fields.

1. Economic cooperation: Russia and Yemen have the potential to expand economic cooperation, especially in the oil and gas industry, in which both countries have significant resources. Russian companies are already working in the oil and gas sector of Yemen, and this cooperation can be further expanded. In addition, agriculture and fisheries may also present opportunities for cooperation, given the traditional development of these industries in Yemen.

2. Trade: is an important area of cooperation between Russia and Yemen. The volume of trade turnover between the two countries has not been very high in recent years, but it still has potential for growth. The main goods that Russia exports to Yemen are petroleum products, metals and food products, as well as many other goods. Yemen, in turn, exports goods such as coffee, textiles, fruits and nuts to Russia. A possible area of cooperation in the field of trade between Russia and

Yemen may be the expansion of the range of goods that can be exported and imported between the two countries, as well as an increase in trade turnover. To do this, work can be carried out to improve the infrastructure for the transportation of goods and to assist entrepreneurs and businesspersons from both countries in establishing contacts and establishing business relations. In addition, work can be carried out to attract investments in trade projects between Russia and Yemen, which can accelerate the development of trade relations between the two countries.

3. Energy: Russia is one of the largest oil and gas producers in the world, and Yemen has significant reserves of oil and natural gas. The development of cooperation in the energy sector can be mutually beneficial for both countries.

4. Science and technology: represent a promising area of cooperation between Russia and Yemen. Russia is one of the world's leading scientific and technological centers and has a well-developed system of scientific research in various fields. Yemen, in turn, has the potential to develop the scientific and technical sector, which can be used to solve various problems faced by Yemeni companies and organizations. A possible area of cooperation in the field of science and technology between Russia and Yemen may be the organization of joint research projects that can lead to the development of new technologies and products that can improve the lives of people in both countries. In addition, Russia can provide assistance to Yemen in developing its scientific and technical infrastructure by training Yemeni scientists and researchers in advanced research methods and helping them gain access to new technologies and equipment.

5. Education and culture: Russia can become an important partner for Yemen in the field of education and culture by providing educational programs and experience in the field of cultural exchange. The countries have common cultural ties, and this can be used to strengthen diplomatic relations between the two countries. Russia can offer Yemen assistance in preserving and restoring historical monuments such as Shibam, a city of high-rise buildings that has been recognized as a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

6. Diplomatic dialogue: Russia and Yemen can cooperate within the framework of diplomatic dialogue on various issues, such as combating international terrorism, resolving conflicts in the region and resolving humanitarian issues. This can be achieved through strengthening the exchange of information and opinions between the two countries, as well as through regular meetings of senior diplomats.

Thus, there is a huge potential for expanding cooperation between Russia and Yemen in various fields. Russia and Yemen can strengthen economic, cultural and security relations, as well as develop diplomatic dialogue and cooperation in the economic, social and humanitarian spheres.

The analysis of the prospects for the development of diplomatic relations between Russia and Yemen should take into account the current situation in the country, the region and the world as a whole, as well as the interests and needs of both countries.

On the one hand, Yemen remains a fragmented and unstable State in which armed conflicts, terrorist acts and a humanitarian crisis continue. In these circumstances, the development of diplomatic relations with Yemen may be a challenge for Russia. However, Russia has experience working in difficult regions and can offer its services in resolving conflicts and restoring peace in Yemen. [4] On the other hand, Russia and Yemen have common interests in the region, including the fight against terrorism, energy security and the development of trade and economic cooperation. In this regard, Russia can use its experience in these areas to strengthen relations with Yemen.

In general, the prospects for the development of diplomatic relations between Russia and Yemen depend on many factors, including political stability in Yemen, the interests and needs of both countries, as well as global changes in the world.

Conclusion. Thus, cooperation between Russia and Yemen has the potential to strengthen in various fields such as economics, trade, science and technology, education and culture, energy and tourism. Both countries have their own strengths and achievements in various fields, which can be a starting point for the development of cooperation. Russia and Yemen already have a certain level of cooperation, but much more can be done to strengthen relations between the two countries. It is important to continue working to expand the

exchange of experience and knowledge, strengthen cultural ties, develop economic cooperation and trade, as well as establish contacts between representatives of the business communities and investors of both countries. Successful cooperation between Russia and Yemen can not only improve economic and cultural relations between the two countries, but also contribute to solving common global problems such as the fight against terrorism and stabilization of the situation in the Middle East.

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